

Intracellular Compartments and Protein Sorting

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Cell is the basic unit of life. Cell exists in either prokaryotic or eukaryotic forms. Both the cells are different from each other in structure and function. A bacterium that generally consists of only intracellular compartment covered by a plasma membrane, is an example of prokaryotic cell whereas on the other side eucaryotic cell have membraned compartments that are functionally distinct and have enzymes of its own. It is necessary to study the structure and dynamics of these compartments of cell and role of protein trafficking in order to understand the cytology. These specific proteins confer upon each compartments their defined structural and functional properties. These protein beside acting as organelle specific surface markers, also catalyses the various reactions inside the cell and transports biomolecule selectively into and out of the cell.

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Components of Prokaryotic and Eukaryotic Cells and Their Functions

Cell Component	Function	Present in Prokaryotes?	Present in Animal Cells?	Present in Plant Cells?
Plasma membrane	Separates cell from external environment; controls passage of organic molecules, ions, water, oxygen, and wastes into and out of the cell	Yes	Yes	Yes
Cytoplasm	Provides structure to cell; site of many metabolic reactions; medium in which organelles are found	Yes	Yes	Yes
Nucleoid	Location of DNA	Yes	No	No
Nucleus	Cell organelle that houses DNA and directs synthesis of ribosomes and proteins	No	Yes	Yes
Ribosomes	Protein synthesis	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mitochondria	ATP production/cellular respiration	No	Yes	Yes
Peroxisomes	Oxidizes and breaks down fatty acids and amino acids, and detoxifies poisons	No	Yes	Yes
Vesicles and vacuoles	Storage and transport; digestive function in plant cells	No	Yes	Yes
Centrosome	Unspecified role in cell division in animal cells; source of microtubules in animal cells	No	Yes	No
Lysosomes	Digestion of macromolecules; recycling of worn-out organelles	No	Yes	No
Cell wall	Protection, structural support and maintenance of cell shape	Yes, primarily peptidoglycan in bacteria but not Archaea	No	Yes, primarily cellulose
Chloroplasts	Photosynthesis	No	No	Yes
Endoplasmic reticulum	Modifies proteins and synthesizes lipids	No	Yes	Yes
Golgi apparatus	Modifies, sorts, tags, packages, and distributes lipids and proteins	No	Yes	Yes
Cytoskeleton	Maintains cell's shape, secures organelles in specific positions, allows cytoplasm and vesicles to move within the cell, and enables unicellular organisms to move independently	Yes	Yes	Yes
Flagella	Cellular locomotion	Some	Some	No, except for some plant sperm.
Cilia	Cellular locomotion, movement of particles along extracellular surface of plasma membrane, and filtration	No	Some	No

INTRACELLULAR COMPARTMENT	PERCENTAGE OF TOTAL CELL VOLUME
Cytosol	54
Mitochondria	22
Rough ER cisternae	9
Smooth ER cisternae plus Golgi cisternae	6
Nucleus	6
Peroxisomes	1
Lysosomes	1
Endosomes	1

Table 2. Relative Volumes Occupied by the Major Intracellular Compartments

Protein Sorting

Most of the protein are synthesized in the cytosol by ribosomes except those that are synthesized by ribosome of mitochondria and in case of plant cell, those that are synthesized by ribosome of plastids. The fate of most of the protein are found in the form of sorting signal that guide them to the comparment or location outside the cytosol to nucleus, ER, or any other destination. Those protein that lacks such sorting signals stays behind in the cytosol as permanent residents.

The principle of protein sorting relies on the understanding of the fundamentals of movement of proteins from one portion/ compartment to another. These pathways include gated transport presented by red arrows, transmembrane transport and vesicular transport shown in blue and green color respectively. A signal is always required for either retention or for exit from a compartment.

The various mechanism can be divided into three as describe below:

1. Gated transport
2. Transmembrane transport
3. Vesicular transport

Gated transport: It is most notable at the junction between the nucleus and the cytoplasm, where selected macromolecules are actively

transported while smaller molecules are allowed free passage.

Transmembrane transport involves the participation of membrane-bound protein translocators which actively allow migration of proteins from the cytoplasm to other cellular cavities. It is believed that in many cases some degree of protein unfolding is required.

Vesicular transport does not require the protein molecules to pass through membranes. Instead, it is the membrane that migrates and fuses with other compartments taking the protein along with it, via a process known as pinocytosis. A transport intermediate enclosed with membrane of variable size and shape loads the cargo of molecule from lumen of a compartment by pinching off from its membrane, unloads their cargo into some other compartment by simply fusing with membrane. Movement between the endoplasmic reticulum and the Golgi apparatus occurs in this manner.

As visible from the diagram, from the donor compartment a transport vesicle buds off and fuses with recipient compartment or target compartment discharging the soluble protein. It can be observed that membrane also gets

transferred and the original orientation of both proteins and lipids in the donor-compartment membrane is preserved in the target-compartment membrane. Thus, membrane proteins retain their asymmetric orientation, with the same domains always facing the cytosol.

In all three cases of protein transport, the sorting signals in the transported protein guides the protein transfer. This signal sequence is recognised by protein receptors that are complementary with the signal sequence. Thus, every proteins fate is dependent on the sequence they carry. Eg. A protein to be transported to nucleus must be carrying sorting signal that is recognised by receptor proteins that will allow to pass through the nuclear core complex and if a protein is to be transported directly through the membrane, must be carrying a signal that will allow allowed by translocators present in the membrane to be crossed. Likewise, there are sorting signals also for those protein that will be loaded in a vesicle or will be retained in the compartment.

Signal Sequences and Signal Patches Direct Proteins to the Correct Cellular Address

As discussed in above, protein fate relies on the sorting signal. There are atleast two sorting signals observable in proteins.

1. First is a continuous amino acid stretch of 15-60 residues, some of which are eliminated at the final stage of sorting process by signal peptidase.
2. The second signal patch consists of 3D arranged atoms on the surface of protein during the folding. The amino acid residues that comprise this signal patch can be distant from one another in the linear amino acid sequence, and they generally persist in the finished protein

- A) The signal resides in a single discrete stretch of amino acid sequence, called a signal sequence, that is exposed in the folded protein. Signal sequences often occur at the end of the polypeptide chain (as shown), but they can also be located internally. (B) A signal patch can be formed by the juxtaposition of amino acids from regions that are physically separated before the protein folds (as shown). Alternatively, separate patches on the surface of the folded protein that are spaced a fixed distance apart can form the signal.

Each sequence acting as a sorting signal leads to different destination eg. Protein to be sent to ER will have a N- Terminus sequence composed of 5-10 hydrophobic Amino Acids(AA). Out of the proteins that have specific sequence of 4 AA at C termnius will be recognised as ER resident and returned

FUNCTION OF SIGNAL SEQUENCE	EXAMPLE OF SIGNAL SEQUENCE
Import into nucleus	-Pro-Pro-Lys-Lys-Lys-Arg-Lys-Val-
Export from nucleus	-Leu-Ala-Leu-Lys-Leu-Ala-Gly-Leu-Asp-Ile-
Import into mitochondria	*H ₃ N-Met-Leu-Ser-Leu-Arg-Gln-Ser-Ile-Arg-Phe-Phe-Lys-Pro-Ala-Thr-Arg-Thr-Leu-Cys-Ser-Ser-Arg-Tyr-Leu-Leu-
Import into plastid	*H ₃ N-Met-Val-Ala-Met-Ala-Met-Ala-Ser-Leu-Gln-Ser-Ser-Met-Ser-Ser-Leu-Ser-Leu-Ser-Ser-Asn-Ser-Phe-Leu-Gly-Gln-Pro-Leu-Ser-Pro-Ile-Thr-Leu-Ser-Pro-Phe-Leu-Gln-Gly-
Import into peroxisomes	-Ser-Lys-Leu-COO ⁻
Import into ER	*H ₃ N-Met-Met-Ser-Phe-Val-Ser-Leu-Leu-Leu-Val-Gly-Ile-Leu-Phe-Trp-Ala-Thr-Glu-Ala-Glu-Gln-Leu-Thr-Lys-Cys-Glu-Val-Phe-Gln-
Return to ER	-Lys-Asp-Glu-Leu-COO ⁻

Some characteristic features of the different classes of signal sequences are highlighted in color. Where they are known to be important for the function of the signal sequence, positively charged amino acids are shown in *red* and negatively charged amino acids are shown in *green*. Similarly, important hydrophobic amino acids are shown in *yellow* and hydroxylated amino acids are shown in *blue*. *H₃N indicates the N-terminus of a protein; COO⁻ indicates the C-terminus.

to ER. Similarly, protein that will have +vely charged AA alternating with hydrophobic ones, All sorting signals are recognized by sorting receptors that are complementary to the sorting signals then guide proteins to their appropriate destination, where they unload their cargo. The receptors function catalytically: after completing one round of targeting, they return

to their point of origin to be reused. Most sorting receptors recognize classes of proteins rather than just an individual protein species. They therefore can be viewed as public transportation systems dedicated to delivering groups of components to their correct location in the cell. will be sent to mitochondria. Some of the specific signals are given in the below.